

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

APPROACHES TO MONITORING AND LOGGING IN AUTOMATED TESTING OF FINANCIAL APPLICATIONS

Bobunov A.

*Bachelor's degree,
Moscow University for Industry and Finance "Synergy"*

ABSTRACT

This article examines the integration of monitoring and logging in automated testing for financial applications. It explores the use of advanced monitoring systems and logging mechanisms, and the challenges associated with these technologies. The study highlights how these systems enhance efficiency, ensure compliance, and maintain operational integrity within financial sectors.

Keywords: financial applications, automated testing, monitoring, logging, real-time data, anomaly detection, regulatory compliance.

Introduction

In the fast-paced realm of financial technologies, automated testing (AT) has emerged as a critical component to ensure the reliability and efficiency of financial applications (FA). Monitoring and logging mechanisms provide insights into application performance, help in detecting anomalies, and support compliance with stringent regulatory requirements. They enable continuous improvement through feedback loops essential for agile development environments.

The goal of this article is to delve into the technological underpinnings and strategic implementations of monitoring and logging within the context of AT.

Main part. Current technologies and tools

Technological advancements have profoundly influenced the methods and approaches used in monitoring and logging. **The advent of cloud computing**, for example, has expanded the capabilities of these systems. This has enabled the creation of scalable and flexible monitoring solutions that can dynamically adapt to changing loads and conditions [1].

Big data technologies have also played a pivotal role in transforming monitoring and logging by allowing the handling of vast volumes of data in near real-time. Tools such as Apache Kafka and Apache Hadoop facilitate efficient data ingestion and processing, enabling more sophisticated analytics and deeper insights into application performance and user interactions.

The integration of **artificial intelligence and machine learning** has introduced predictive capabilities into monitoring tools, allowing for the proactive management of system health [2]. These technologies enable the identification of patterns and trends that predict system failures before they occur, thus minimizing downtime and improving service reliability. The ongoing technological evolution continues to reshape these tools and methods, promising even greater efficiencies and capabilities in the future.

Monitoring methods

One fundamental approach in application monitoring is the use of **health checks and performance counters**. These techniques involve routine checks that assess application components (like servers, databases, and network infrastructure) to ensure they are operating within predefined thresholds. Companies such as **Microsoft (USA) and SAP (Germany)** extensively integrate monitoring systems like Microsoft Azure Monitor and SAP Focused Run [3]. These applications are designed to preemptively address issues before they affect the user experience. Azure Monitor, for example, provides comprehensive capabilities for collecting, analyzing, and acting on telemetry from cloud and on-premises environments, helping to maximize the performance and availability of applications (figure 1).

Figure 1. Example of analyzing metrics of a FA using Azure Monitor [4]

Similarly, SAP Focused Run is tailored for high-volume monitoring needs, offering rich insights into operations and supporting proactive management of SAP landscapes.

Machine learning models, particularly those utilizing supervised learning techniques, are deployed to enhance monitoring efficiency. Services like Google Cloud’s AI Platform (USA) and Amazon Web Services’ SageMaker (USA) provide robust environments for training and deploying these models, facilitating their integration into monitoring workflows. These tools help in rapidly identifying and responding to operational issues, thus maintaining system stability and improving overall performance.

To effectively manage the vast amounts of data generated by monitoring systems, **data visualization** has become an indispensable tool. Platforms like Grafana (Sweden) and Tableau (USA) offer sophisticated visualization capabilities that allow IT teams to see trends and patterns that would be difficult to discern through raw data alone [5]. These tools enable the creation of dashboards that can display metrics such as transaction volumes, response times, system uptime, and error rates in an intuitive format. Real-time data streaming and interactive dashboards ensure that deviations from the norm are quickly identified and addressed.

Critical to the monitoring process is the ability of systems to notify personnel of detected failures in a timely manner. This is typically achieved through the implementation of integrated **alert systems** within

monitoring frameworks. Splunk (USA), for example, uses advanced indexing and search capabilities to parse through large datasets and generate alerts based on specific criteria such as error messages or performance dips. Notification systems are designed to escalate issues to the appropriate channels, ensuring rapid response to potential disruptions. These alerts can be configured to trigger under certain conditions, which are often customizable, allowing teams to prioritize issues based on severity and impact.

The methodologies and techniques utilized for monitoring in the context of AT of FA are crucial in safeguarding operational continuity and security. By leveraging advanced algorithms, sophisticated data visualization tools, and effective failure notification systems, financial institutions can achieve high levels of application performance and reliability.

Logging strategies

In the realm of AT for FA, logging not only serves as a record of events but also as a crucial tool for problem prevention and diagnosis. Effective strategies are essential for creating comprehensive and informative logs that can be analyzed to detect anomalies, trace errors, and understand system behavior under various test scenarios. In Table 1, a detailed breakdown of logging approaches is presented, outlining their applications and benefits.

Table 1

Strategic approaches to log structuring for enhanced informativeness in automated FA testing

Approach	Description	Benefits	Examples
Structured logging	Logs are formatted in a standardized, easily parsable format such as JSON, with clear labeling of log type and content.	Facilitates automated parsing and analysis; enhances readability.	Google Cloud Logging (USA)
Centralized logging	Logs from all systems and components are aggregated into a single, centralized system for unified access and analysis.	Simplifies management and analysis across distributed systems.	Splunk (USA)
Correlation logging	Logs include unique identifiers for transactions or sessions, allowing related events to be connected across the system.	Enables tracking of user sessions and transaction flows; useful for debugging and auditing [6]	ELK Stack (Elasticsearch, Logstash, Kibana; USA)
Contextual information	Logs are enriched with context such as timestamp, user ID, and system metrics at the time of the event .	Provides comprehensive insights for diagnosing issues.	Datadog (USA)
Severity levels	Logs are categorized by severity levels (e.g., info, warning, error), making it easier to filter and prioritize issues.	Aids in quick identification of critical issues versus informational messages.	Apache Log4j (USA)

From the author's perspective, strategically structuring logs is about transforming them from mere data records into a proactive tool for system management and error resolution. This approach is validated by the successful experiences of companies such as Google (USA) and Alibaba (China), where advanced logging strategies have markedly improved the efficiency of troubleshooting and system analysis. These corpora-

tions utilize structured and centralized logging to effectively manage their extensive, complex systems, ensuring transparency and manageability. This confirms the critical role of structured logging in providing insights that enable rapid, informed decision-making in AT environments. By adopting these methods, financial institutions can enhance their ability to preemptively address potential issues, thereby maintaining high levels of system reliability and user satisfaction.

Integration and automation

The integration of monitoring and logging systems with AT processes represents a significant advancement in the testing of FA. This synergy not only streamlines workflows but also enhances the accuracy and efficiency of testing by providing real-time data.

One of the exemplary integrations is the use of Jenkins, an automation server, with monitoring tools like Nagios (USA) or Zabbix (Latvia). Jenkins can be configured to initiate diagnostic tests automatically based on real-time alerts from these monitoring systems. For instance, if Nagios detects a performance drop below a specified threshold, it can trigger a battery of tests to identify and address the root cause. This proactive testing approach helps maintain system performance and significantly reduces downtime.

Financial institutions also commonly integrate Splunk (USA) for logging with Selenium (USA), an AT framework. Splunk collects and analyzes logs generated during Selenium tests, providing insights into application behavior under test conditions. This integration is invaluable for spotting patterns that could indicate potential failures or security issues, enabling teams to make informed decisions quickly.

Python script example for AT with selenium:

```
from selenium import webdriver

# Set up the Selenium WebDriver
driver = webdriver.Chrome('/path/to/chromedriver')

# Define a function to perform automated tests and
log results
def perform_test(url):
    try:
        driver.get(url)
        # Simulate interactions and checks
        driver.find_element_by_id('login').click()
        print("Test passed: Login button clicked")
    except Exception as e:
        print(f"Test failed: {str(e)}")

# URL to test
```

```
test_url = 'http://example.com'
perform_test(test_url)
```

```
# Clean up and close the browser
driver.quit()
```

This simple Python script uses Selenium for automated web testing by interacting with a web page and performing a specific action.

Scripts and automated tools are pivotal in enhancing testing efficacy by automating repetitive tasks and aggregating results for comprehensive analysis. PowerShell scripts, for example, are widely used to automate the deployment of testing environments and to manage log extraction processes [7]. These scripts facilitate interactions with both the operating system and the application layer, automating tasks like database setups, server processes initiation, and logging system states before and after tests.

Automated analysis tools such as IBM's Rational Quality Manager (USA) and CA's Test Data Manager (USA) further augment these processes with sophisticated capabilities to analyze test outputs and logs. Equipped with algorithms to detect anomalies and patterns indicative of underlying system issues, these tools improve their predictive accuracy over time through learning from historical data, which is indispensable for preemptive testing and maintenance [8].

The integration of monitoring and logging with AT processes is foundational to a robust testing infrastructure in the finance sector. By leveraging scripts and automated tools, financial institutions can achieve not only high reliability and compliance with regulations but also maintain agility in their software development cycles.

Challenges and issues analysis

While the integration of monitoring and logging systems with AT processes has brought substantial benefits to the finance sector, there are inherent challenges and limitations associated with these technologies. In Table 2, a detailed analysis of these challenges is presented to provide a comprehensive understanding of the obstacles faced by financial institutions.

Table 2.

Analysis of challenges and issues in integrating new monitoring and logging technologies

Challenge	Description	Impact	Mitigation strategies
Legacy system compatibility	Older financial systems often struggle to integrate with modern monitoring and logging tools, leading to gaps in data and functionality.	Limits the effectiveness of new technologies, potentially increasing operational risks.	Gradual integration, use of adapters, and incremental upgrades.
Data silos	Data stored in isolated systems complicates unified monitoring and analysis.	Hampers real-time decision-making and can lead to inconsistent data insights [9].	Implementation of middleware solutions to integrate disparate systems.
Scalability concerns	As financial institutions grow, their systems must handle larger volumes of data and more complex network structures.	Systems may become overwhelmed, leading to reduced performance and potential outages.	Adopting scalable cloud solutions and elastic computing resources.
Security and privacy issues	Integrating new technologies can introduce vulnerabilities, especially if not properly managed.	Exposes institutions to cybersecurity threats and data breaches.	Rigorous security assessments and continuous monitoring of security protocols [10].
Regulatory compliance	New technologies must comply with financial regulations which may limit their use or configuration.	Compliance failures can result in legal penalties and damage to reputation.	Ensuring new systems are configurable to meet various regulatory standards.

From the author's perspective, while the integration of advanced monitoring and logging systems presents a transformative opportunity for the finance sector, it also introduces several complex challenges. Leading financial institutions that successfully navigate these challenges often implement comprehensive risk management strategies and invest in continuous training for their IT staff. This proactive approach not only mitigates the risks associated with new technology integration but also ensures that these institutions remain agile and responsive to evolving market demands.

Conclusions

The integration of monitoring and logging systems with AT processes in the realm of FA has proven to be a pivotal development, significantly enhancing the efficiency, accuracy, and reliability of testing protocols. These systems facilitate real-time data provision, which streamlines workflows and supports rigorous compliance with regulatory standards, ensuring that financial institutions can maintain high operational continuity and secure environments for financial transactions.

Through the successful implementation of advanced tools like Jenkins, Nagios, and Splunk, in conjunction with robust AT frameworks such as Selenium, financial institutions have been able to not only preemptively identify and mitigate potential failures but also refine their overall testing and monitoring strategies. The use of Python and PowerShell scripts has further augmented this integration, automating repetitive tasks and enabling sophisticated data aggregation and analysis that drive proactive decision-making processes.

References

- Mishra, L., & Kaushik, V. (2023). Application of blockchain in dealing with sustainability issues and challenges of the financial sector. *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, 13(3), 1318–1333.
- Patrick Loic Foalem, Foutse Khomh, Heng Li, Studying logging practice in machine learning-based applications, *Information and Software Technology*, Volume 170, 2024.
- Puthiyavan Udayakumar; Kathiravan Udayakumar, Design and Deploy Azure Web Application Firewall and Monitor Networks, in *MCA Microsoft Certified Associate Azure Network Engineer Study Guide: Exam AZ-700*, Wiley, 2023, pp. 543-614
- Analyze metrics with Azure Monitor metrics explorer / Microsoft URL: <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/azure-monitor/essentials/analyze-metrics> (date of application: 19.04.2024).
- Artemov A. PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES IN DATA ENGINEERING: OVERVIEW, TRENDS AND PRACTICAL APPLICATION // *Innovatsionnaya nauka*. 2023. №10-2.
- Calderon, G., del Campo, G., Saavedra, E. et al. Monitoring Framework for the Performance Evaluation of an IoT Platform with Elasticsearch and Apache Kafka. *Inf Syst Front* (2023).
- Bukhtueva I. THE IMPACT OF AI TECHNOLOGIES ON BUSINESS PERFORMANCE // *Vestnik nauki* №3 (72) vol. 5. pp. 467 - 476. 2024 г. ISSN 2712-8849

8. Tiumentsev D.V., Shaikhulov E.A. Synthesis of DevOps and ML: optimizing IT workflow // Modern scientific researches and innovations. 2024. № 2.
9. Ogarkov A. Enhancing commercial effectiveness in pharmaceuticals: a case study on the implementation of successful sales and marketing strategies / A. Ogarkov // Issues of management and economics: current state of current problems: collection. Art. based on materials from the LXXX International Scientific and Practical Conference "Issues of Management and Economics: Current State of Current Problems." – No. 2(71). – M., Ed. "Internauka", 2024.
10. Tiumentsev, D. Application of cryptographic technologies for information protection in cloud services / D. Tiumentsev // Stolypin Annals. – 2024. – Vol. 6, No. 3. – EDN EDLWAT.